

<Exhibition and Media Reviews>

edited by Michael Rhode

***On the Money: Cartoons for the New Yorker.* Jennifer Tonkovich. New York, NY: The Morgan Library and Museum, Jan. 23-May 24, 2009. <<http://www.themorgan.org/exhibitions/exhibition.asp?id=14>>**

The Morgan Library and Museum is an impressive cluster of buildings on Madison Avenue between 36th and 37th Streets. It is, more or less, literally the House of Morgan. Visiting this complex to view an exhibition of cartoons skewering the pretensions and foibles of the moneyed classes at a time of financial crisis seemed rich with irony and perhaps itself a good topic for a cartoon.

The exhibition was in the old reading room of the Morgan, a grand room that has the scale of a boardroom. Fittingly the first cartoon encountered was set in just such a room. Gluyas Williams's 1927 "Influence of the Huddle System on a Big Business Conference" shows a group of businessmen huddling together in a corner. The football metaphor was no doubt as appropriate then as it is now, but an image of business types huddling also registers now as something else -- if not huddled players, then at least shamed bankers.

The exhibition though lacked a didactic tone. The gentle humor of the *New Yorker* did a lot of heavy lifting in poking criticism at what, perhaps from the perspective of say, a Morgan, looked to be the aggressive déclassé pursuit of money by parvenus. William Hamilton works this vein with distinction and his cartoons comprised some nine percent of the exhibit. In a May 1987 cartoon, Hamilton has a fresh-faced young woman say to her rather smug looking Yalely boyfriend "That is incredible. Do you know that I, too, want as much as I can get as fast as I can get it?" The combination of ingénue visual with grasping words sets up the joke about the empty visions of the privileged young.

There were some great lines in the cartoons exhibited: Stan Hunt's "They control ninety-six percent of the market in something nobody wants anymore," Robert Weber's "It's up to you now, Miller. The only thing that can save us is an accounting breakthrough," and another of his, "Your Honor, my client now realizes that his actions in the Unotek buyout and his transfers of funds to Swiss bank accounts were dreadfully immature." But great lines such as those, in combination with visuals, are what make them so funny. In the first example, the washed-up capitalists have the embittered look one would expect of former

grantees and the commentators the happy smug look of those defining themselves against others' misfortune. That Weber's accountant, who has to carry the weight for the adventures of his company, is a stereotypical nerdy figure strengthens the laugh by reminding us that the backroom boys, nerds though they be, are just as likely to cook the books. Likewise the wonderful simple line that conveys a middle-aged man trying to exude innocent boyish charm in Weber's cartoon makes that cartoon laugh-out-loud worthy.

In this case putting a medium designed for print on a museum's walls made sense. Containing just 79 cartoons, the exhibition concentrated the mind nicely. Reading omnibus volumes of *New Yorker* cartoons is often an overwhelming experience, but this arrangement let the viewer take in a discrete set of cartoons at a leisurely pace. The exhibit also included some examples showing how cartoons are shaped through an exchange between creator and editor. Speaking to the exhibition curator Jennifer Tonkovich, I commented that I would have liked to see more of this process and perhaps even some teasing out of the balance between words and visuals. Perhaps that will provide the subject of a future exhibit drawing on the Morgan Library and Museums collection of cartoons.

Ian Gordon

***The Art of Watchmen.* New York City: Museum of Comic and Cartoon Art. March 6-May 2, 2009.**

The Art of Watchmen exhibit at the Museum of Comic and Cartoon Art vividly added another dimension to Alan Moore and Dave Gibbons' groundbreaking graphic novel. The exhibit showcased art from both the comic book series with Gibbons' original artwork, reproductions of concept sketches, and color guides from colorist John Higgins, and also photograph character portraits from the Warner Bros. movie adaptation taken by Clay Enos, still photographer on the film project.

When first seeing the exhibit, this reviewer noted how strongly the show's design echoed the *Watchmen* themes and tropes. From yellow walls, to a column decorated in a collage of panels from the comic, to a clock perched overhead, the design provided context for the art on display, and surrounded the visitor in the *Watchmen* world so that one could envision the comic or movie in ones' mind without much effort. Gibbons' showcased artwork consisted of original covers from the series, arranged in such a manner that it gave the viewer a sense that each picture was the number on a clock, all building up to the cover of issue #12, which showed the clock about to strike midnight and thus doomsday.

Juxtaposed next to the comic artwork were close-up character portraits